

Agroforestry Map

as of December 31, 2025 | February 2026

Overview of agroforestry areas in Germany 2025

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The Agroforestry Map of Europe provides an overview of existing and planned agroforestry systems, research institutions, education and information centres, and stakeholders in the upstream and downstream sectors of agroforestry. This evaluation focuses on Germany.

New entries can be added on an ongoing basis, so that their number is constantly growing.

This overview publishes selected content from the map entries once a year. This edition refers to the status as of December 31, 2025.

Publisher

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Dear readers,

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1 Proportions of agroforestry system types

By the cut-off date of December 31, 2025, a total of **239 agroforestry systems** had been entered in the Agroforestry Map for Germany*.

Of these, 86 areas (36%) are silvopastoral systems, meaning that the entries mainly refer to systems in which trees and shrubs have been planted on grassland or combined with livestock farming. 112 areas (47%) are silvoarable systems, 33 areas (14%) are agrosilvopastoral systems, and the remaining eight areas are "other" agroforestry areas, such as forest gardens (3%).

The total area of agroforestry systems marked on the map is **2,092 ha**, with agroforestry woodlands accounting for **424 ha**.

Figure 1: Agroforestry system area by federal state in ha.

Figure3: Total area and proportion of agroforestry woodlands per system in 2025 (in ha). The hatched area represents the proportion of woodland, while the solid area represents the main crop.

*The data in the agroforestry map is not representative and does not constitute a complete database of agroforestry areas in Germany. It only shows those areas that have been submitted to DeFAF e.V. by land users and other individuals through independent entries on the map. The actual number and total area of agroforestry systems is therefore likely to be considerably larger, as not all systems are entered on the agroforestry map.

2 Proportion of agroforestry systems in the federal states

The total area of registered agroforestry land is largest in **Brandenburg**, at around **475 ha**, which accounts for 36.6‰ of Brandenburg's agricultural land.

Lower Saxony and **Bavaria** come in second and third place with 320 and 289 ha respectively.

No registrations have been made in Berlin, Bremen, or Hamburg to date.

Figure 4: Proportion of agroforestry system types in the 2025 Agroforestry Map of Germany.

Figure 5: Proportion of agroforestry area in relation to agricultural land by federal state.

Compared to the other federal states, **Saarland** has the smallest area of agroforestry systems to date, at 15 ha, but it ranks second in terms of the relative share of available agricultural land, at 20.7‰.

Hesse and **Saxony** rank third and fourth in Germany in terms of the relative share of agroforestry in agricultural land.

The pie charts in the map of the federal states illustrate the total number of agroforestry systems using different sizes. The respective proportions in the pie charts represent the proportional area size of the agroforestry system types (silvoarable, silvopastoral, agro-silvopastoral, and other systems). All four types of agroforestry systems are found in five federal states.

Figure 6: Proportions of agroforestry system types by federal state. The size of the pie charts shows the respective total area.

3 Use of tree species in agroforestry systems

In the registered agroforestry systems, the most commonly used **tree species** are poplar, walnut, and cherry, which are used in 120, 111, and 95 of the registered agroforestry systems, respectively. A total of 78 different trees were classified (some named only by genus).

Table1: Tree species in the agroforestry map that were planted in at least two systems.

Tree species*	Number of systems	Proportion	Tree species*	Number of systems	Proportion
Poplar	12	50.2	Paulownia	8	3.3
Walnut	111	46.4	Pecan	6	2.5
Cherry / Wild cherry	95	39.7	Small-leaved lime	6	2.5
Apple	89	37.2	Nashi pear	5	2.1
Pear	73	30.5	Butternut	5	2.1
Plum	72	30.1	Kiwi	5	2.1
Chestnut	72	30.1	Hybrid walnut	5	2.1
Willow	58	24.3	Pine	4	1.7
Wild service tree	49	20.5	European larch	4	1.7
Rowan (mountain ash)	45	18.8	Field maple	4	1.7
Maple	36	15.1	Italian alder	4	1.7
Alder	34	14.2	Olive	4	1.7
Service tree	31	13.0	Sycamore	4	1.7
Turkish hazel / tree hazel	25	10.5	Pomegranate	3	1.3
White mulberry	25	10.5	Aspen	3	1.3
Black mulberry	24	10.0	English oak	3	1.3
Oak	23	9.6	Red beech	3	1.3
Quince	23	9.6	Silver fir	3	1.3
Wild pear	22	9.2	Hickory nut	3	1.3
Common fig	19	7.9	Honey locust	3	1.3
Peach	19	7.9	Sour cherry	3	1.3
Bird cherry	18	7.5	Honey tree / stinking ash	3	1.3
Hornbeam	18	7.5	Sessile oak	3	1.3
European wild apple	16	6.7	Black walnut	3	1.3
Linden	16	6.7	Balsam poplar	2	0.8
Birch	15	6.3	Black poplar	2	0.8
Apricot	12	5.0	Black poplar × Maximowicz pop.	2	0.8
Ash	12	5.0	Black alder	2	0.8
Persimmon	12	5.0	Fluttering elm	2	0.8
Service tree	12	5.0%	Grey alder	2	0.8
Medlar	11	4.6	Heartnut / Japanese walnut	2	0.8
Black locust / false acacia	1	4.6	Pistachio	2	0.8
Almond	9	3.8	Silver birch	2	0.8
Elm	9	3.8	Silver poplar	2	0.8

*In the case of some tree species, no further distinction was made between individual species within the genus.

Among the **shrub species** (including semi-shrubs), hazelnut, elderberry, and raspberry are the most commonly used in the registered agroforestry systems, with 67, 62, and 42 mentions, respectively (Table 2). Shrubs are used in every second agroforestry system in Germany (52%). The total number of shrub species amounts to 50 different shrubs (in some cases only the genus is named).

Table2: Shrub species in the agroforestry map that were planted in at least two systems.

Shrub species*	Number of systems	Proportion	Shrub species*	Number of systems	Proportion
Hazelnut	67	28.	Pawpaw	11	4.6
Elderberry	62	25.9	Mayberry	10	4.2
Raspberry	42	17.6	Jostaberry	10	4.2
Dog rose, rose hip	39	16.3	Alder buckthorn	7	2.9
Hawthorn	36	15.1	Privet	6	2.5
European cornel	35	14.6	Goji	6	2.5
Rock pear	30	12.6	Kiwiberry	6	2.5
Blackberry	29	12.1	Pea shrub	6	2.5
Currants	28	11.7	Snowberry	6	2.5
Dogwood	27	11.3	Blackthorn	3	1.3
Sea buckthorn	26	10.9	Loganberry	3	1.3
Sloe	22	9.2	Schisandra	3	1.3
Gooseberry	22	9.2	Scottish broom	3	1.3
Silverberry	20	8.4	Sichuan pepper	3	1.3
Chokeberry, aronia	20	8.4	Common broom	2	0.8
Figs	18	7.5	Mixed snowball	2	0.8
Fly honeysuckle	14	5.9	Kamchatka honeysuckle	2	0.8
Grapes	14	5.9	Bare rock pear	2	0.8
Spindle	12	5.0	Tayberry	2	0.8
Woolly snowball	12	5.	Whistling bush	2	0.8
Bilberry, lingonberry, blueberry	11	4.6	Common juniper	2	0.8

*In the case of some shrub species, no further distinction was made between individual species within the genus.

4 Establishment of agroforestry systems over time

With 29 new areas, 2023 has seen the most agroforestry systems established to date. In 2020, the largest total area of registered agroforestry systems was added (312 ha).

Figure 7: Time series of agroforestry system establishment since 1993 and area in ha.

AGROFORESTRY MAP

Who are you?

www.defaf.de

You are involved in agroforestry in the field of:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trees & crops (silvoarable) Trees & livestock (silvopastoral) Trees & crops & livestock (agrosilvopastoral) other e.g. Forest Garden 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consulting & services Research & education Interested
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Register on the map today to become part of the agroforestry community.

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The German Association for Agroforestry

Are you interested in agroforestry but still have questions?

Feel free to contact us.

DeFAF e.V. is the central point of contact for all questions relating to agroforestry in Germany. The association is committed to promoting the wider use of this form of sustainable land use. The aim is to improve networking between farmers, stakeholders from the food industry, politics and administration, nature conservation and other interested parties. Because only

by working together can we develop practical and sustainable solutions for agriculture.

Many members of the non-profit DeFAF e.V. work on a voluntary basis in various specialist areas – from consulting and education to economic, ecological, and legal issues. Do you have any questions or ideas? Then get in touch with us.

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